

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Rasulova Sohiba Ulugbekovna

IMPROVING SECONDARY SCHOOL CHILDREN'S SPEAKING SKILL

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